

Article: **SPRAWL AND HUMAN MISERY: AN
ECOMARXIST READING OF ARTHUR MILLER'S
DEATH OF A SALESMAN**

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SPRAWL AND HUMAN MISERY: AN ECOMARXIST READING OF ARTHUR MILLER'S DEATH OF A SALESMAN

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ABSTRACT

The study explores connection between emerging Markets and human misery in *Death of a Salesman*, focusing to prove Market reigns supremacy in the lives of Americans under the guise of 'modernity'. The new Split in the personality of characters in the play is tallied to the 'changing times'. The so-called progress has created an 'industrialized world' where the characters are unwillingly voyaging in the economic direction. The protagonists in the narrative are depicted as disconnected from the natural world, instead actively participating in market, pursuing marketecture, and contributing to the prevalence of consumerism within a society influenced by marketecture. The phenomenon emerges from urban sprawl disrupts the ecological equilibrium, leading to detrimental consequences for the individuals in United States. The phenomenon of urban expansion significantly impacts the development of characters and their outlook on life, exerting influences across many levels of society, ranging from private residences to larger communal spaces.

Keywords: Market, Sprawl, Consumer culture, Marketecture, Depression

Introduction:

Arthur Miller, a great and all-time American writer, remained dominant throughout the 20th century and passed away in the early 21st century; he was born in 1915 and lived until 2005. Despite everything, the tragic masterpiece that was *Death of a Salesman* has a long-lived popularity; however, he passed. Miller¹ dramatizes the conflict between the desire for material success and the pursuit of adventure and happiness in the American consciousness in the play. Finally, through the tragic story of an elderly traveling salesman, he profoundly reveals the very true picture of the society in which he was living, and more importantly, provides the ways to understand the society. Arthur Miller's *Death of a Salesman* has been explored from a wide range of theoretical perspectives, including

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sociolinguistic analysis², and more importantly, it has been linked with the socio-economic perspective of society, presenting through capitalism³; however, when the text is evaluated, psychoanalytic theory⁴ and interpersonal acceptance and rejection theory are also given respectable positions.⁵

In fact, there are far too many lapses noted about the masterwork for those who already analyzed, to be addressed. One of the investigations in this brief discussion will not use a theory; rather, it will carefully read the text to invest topical Eco-Marxist imprints hidden between the Traditional Marxism⁶ was the philosophy that Karl Marx (1818-1883) and Friedrich Engels (1820-1895) established⁷. It was a highly powerful and influential intellectual force during the first half of the twentieth century. *Death of a Salesman*⁸ by Arthur Miller portrays Willy Loman's attempt to realize the American dream is extremely realistic, because of Miller's efforts. Willy, the tragic figure, spends his whole life clinging to the notion that he will one day realize the American ideal. He believes that the United States of America is the best country in the world and that as long as one is prepared to take risks, there is no doubt that he would be successful living in that country. Willy says that "the most significant things can happen! and we couldn't agree more"⁹.

He never fails to exhibit an excessive amount of self-importance and unwarranted optimism. For instance, even though he is nothing more than a typical traveling salesman and the company his close buddy Charley owns is doing well, he is convinced that he would one day run a significantly more successful company than Charley's. In his mind, his brother Ben is the living manifestation of the success that one can achieve by following the American ideal. Ben is an extremely successful businessman. When he was seventeen, he traveled to Africa's Gold Coast to work in the diamond mines and strolled into the surrounding bush. Four years later, Ben emerged from the forest, having amassed a considerable fortune. Willy considers him a hero and looks up to him. When he initially presents Ben to his sons, he does so with a sense of pride, saying things like, This is your Uncle Ben, a great man!¹⁰

In addition, the achievement of Willy's goals for his children is an essential component of his "American dream". Willy constantly thinks his sons are better than others, even if he arrogantly believes he is better than Charley. He has this recurring dream that his older son, Biff, has extremely high hopes for himself. In this dream, for example, Biff receives scholarship offers from three universities, and he will become a famous football player. Since they were very little, Willy has been instilling in his children a sense of excitement and enthusiasm for Willy's business endeavors. He imparts this wisdom upon them, saying, ... the person who makes an appearance in the business world and the one who develops personal interest are the ones who succeed in the business world¹¹. He instills in his sons the desire to grow up to be great men of the future and uses Ben as an example to teach them this lesson. During the conversation with Ben in which he discusses how and what he should teach his boys, he forcefully reveals these thoughts, saying,... was

rich! I want (Willy's two sons) to have that kind of character, and I hope to instill it in them!¹²

In his play *Death of a Salesman*, Arthur Miller brilliantly brings out the desire that people have to achieve material success through exciting experiences, which is, in reality, a result of commercial and capitalist societies. In contrast to the feudal society, which is strictly stratified, the capitalist society gives everyone an equal opportunity to be successful. This is because everything that is bought and sold in the Market is conducted on an equal basis. Therefore, if someone is more intelligent than other people, more aggressive than other people, and more diligent than other people, he stands a better chance of becoming more established. Also, Willy's excessive optimism is heavily impacted by the established ideals in the United States throughout the late 1940s. This was when the United States had won the major triumphs in both world wars; thus, the country was riding high on its success. The United States was able to amass such a large amount of cash through the purchase of less expensive enslaved Black people at the start of its history and from the sale of weaponry throughout both of world wars. After the culmination of the Second World War, the United States of America ascended as the preeminent global power, with the United States dollar assuming the status of a universally recognized currency. As a result, the American government mistakenly believed that it could easily exert its will over the majority of countries throughout the world. An old proverb goes, when an American sneezes, the rest of the world will catch the flu.

In view of the above, the present research paper seeks to establish a connection between emerging Markets and human misery in the play *Death of the Salesman*. It aims to prove that the Market reigns supreme in the lives of Americans under the guise of 'modernity' and development. The new Split in the personality of characters in the play is tallied to the 'changing times'. The so-called progress has created an 'industrialized world' where the characters are unwillingly voyaging in the economic direction. In the past, Nature was the source of survival for these characters, which no longer holds sway.

Literature Review:

Earle Draper, who was noted by Nechyba and Randall¹³ as being the first person to use the term "sprawl," did so in 1937 at a national meeting of planners. As per his assertion, the city's expansion resulted in a sprawling effect that rendered the surrounding countryside aesthetically unappealing, economically inefficient in terms of public services, and questionable social values." He goes on to claim that large swaths of land that were once lush with vegetation have been transformed into immense deserts filled with smog, and that every day, additional land at the rate of 3,000 acres is disappearing. Draper intended to convey that the deterioration of the natural environment is a reason for concern and that it looks to be the result of an infinite number of interconnected factors. In the eyes of the market, the natural environment, which assigns a monetary value to

everything, is first and foremost real estate, and secondarily, the worth of all of the natural resources contained within it, such as lumber, minerals, oil, and so on. The objective of the Market is to turn the natural environment into a commodity, whether that commodity is the landscape itself, the lumber cut down from it, or the tract houses erected upon it. The market can make a profit off of the environment in this way.

Significant advancements were achieved in the field of science and technology over the course of the previous century. The continuous enhancement of production infrastructure, spanning from developing individual transistors to establishing global networking, is truly remarkable. However, it is disheartening to consider humans' impact on the natural world. To put a stop to a cycle that started with nature in its purest form, older components are thrown away when they become unnecessary, worn out, or have served their function. The utilization of natural resources resulted in the production of goods, which in turn led to the accumulation of waste. The market economy is a vortex hell that ingests natural resources, digests them, and expels mountains of waste into the environment.

In his scholarly publication, Stiles¹⁴, an eco-Marxist, contends that the market has engendered an inequitable relationship between the market economy and the natural environment. The market economy, an inherent product of natural systems, is causing detrimental environmental effects, leading to a systemic self-destructive behaviour. The consequences of this unregulated development have had a profound and detrimental impact.

According to Kunstler¹⁵, a vital approach has been made regarding the absence of any empirical data that is more significant, widespread, and lamentable than the tragedy that has afflicted the American landscape in terms of substantiating the risks associated with an unregulated market. The nation, which was formerly characterized by its aesthetic appeal, is presently experiencing a huge expansion of urban development that spans from coastal areas to inland regions. A cursory circumnavigation through any American city puts a traveler in an identical world of strip malls, chain stores, fast food restaurants, and tract houses with artificial names, all converted by miles of blacktop and utility cables and submerged in lousy air in almost all cases. Kunstler¹⁶ notes that business magnates bulldoze the countryside using the ruse of progress, but they never answer the question of "whose progress and at what expense?" Americans are facing the paradox of progress compromising human happiness. Material development creates an environment that depresses individuals, and sprawl is the physical manifestation of that depressing environment.

Anwar¹⁷ in his paper "Capitalism versus Narcissism" is about *Death of a Salesman* as a Psychoanalytic Study, about the economic disparities in the play that can also be taken for the so-called uncontrolled sprawl; indeed, the prevailing influence is exerted by market forces rather than city planners and regulators. Akin to commercial media or

market culture in general, it works to maximize profit; hence, it strips the architecture of higher principles. The prioritization of profit over artistic value results in the emergence in a form of architecture attire known as “marketecture,”¹⁸ which can be likened to pornography, focusing on commercialism rather than aesthetic merit. The onslaught of Marketecture has caused not only the erosion of landscape; it has completely replaced landscape with marketspace, adversely impacting human health. The effects of sprawl on humans can be easily evaluated, unlike the effects of stress. Even if it is not the primary cause, it contributes to a wide range of negative social outcomes. The impact on human health has been related to various factors, including obesity, pollution, violence, stress, and depression.

Sprawl and human misery with referent to Eco-Marxist perspective in *Death of a salesman*

People are fragmented into distinct productive practices in a commercial environment due to the isolating effects of sprawl, which atomizes civilization. As a result, sprawl is just getting started, and it feels like a bulldozer is leveling the forest so that tract houses may be built. It is conceivable that there will be a shift in the mood of society and an progress in the market temperature. The final stage of this evolution occurs when the stars vanish and are replaced by fluorescent light, indicating a reduction in the scope of one’s perspective. It has become impossible to look past one’s own self-interest. As a result, Howard views Willy Loman as nothing more than an object, and he gets rid of him.

When constructing a setting for human habitation, traditional and settled communities balanced the natural and the man-made elements of the environment. According to Frank Wright¹⁹, a successful structure is organically incorporated into its location and enhances the natural environment. Whereas the setting of the play and stage directions exhibit that Willy Loman’s house and surrounding buildings are not endemic to the environment. An elaborate stage direction helps the audience, and readers see the difference in the present and past imagined by Willy Loman. The play starts with the melody being played on the flute. When the curtain rises, we are shown the salesman’s house. The stage direction shows, “we are aware of towering, angular shapes behind it, surrounding it”. An expressionistic trope of “an angry glow of orange” is shown over the surrounding area²⁰. As more light appears, we see a row of apartment houses around the small, fragile home. The entire setting is wholly or, in some places, partially transparent. The house’s roofline is one-dimensional; we see the apartment buildings under it and over it.

Willy Loman’s home is analogous to a hamburger from a fast food restaurant in that it is low-priced, mass-produced, and devoid of any nutritional value. Every example is identical to the one that came before it to reduce the amount of money spent on design and speed up production. Because even a few cents add up quickly on an assembly line, extraordinary lengths are gone to cut costs everywhere. As a result, minimal framing,

paper-thin walls, and other materials are selected to last one week longer than the new home guarantee. Because the shower is leaking, Linda is constantly nagging him to fix it. In a state of exasperation, Willy exclaims, all of a sudden, everything falls to pieces! the plumbing company should be taken to court. I had just about finished putting it in when suddenly it started falling apart.

The sprawl makes the entire building site subservient to market philosophy. The entire future community is leveled on day one rather than attempting to save trees, which are tough to work around. Following that, the land is subdivided into lots of varying sizes. The next step is to plant a few seedlings, which results in creating a market for tree farmers and the commercialization of yet another component of nature. The design of individual structures does not consider how they will interact with their environment. The concept of “assembly-line construction” is imposed upon various settings, notwithstanding their inherent diversity. This assembly line Marketecture presupposes that, because humans in industrialized era and space while eating, shopping, and living, no longer need beauty in their surroundings. Willy complains persistently, “the way they boxed us in here. Bricks and windows... windows and bricks”²¹.

Whenever he has a conversation with Biff, he comes across as hopeless and exasperated. “for the love of God, could you please throw open the window in this room? In her characteristically patient manner, Linda responds, “They’re all open, dear.” Unvaryingly unpleasant things surround the characters: According to what Miller quotes Linda as saying, “we should have bought the land next door.” Then, in response to that, Willy says, “The Street is lined with cars.”²² There isn’t a single solitary molecule of clean air anywhere in the area. There is no longer any growth of grass, and you cannot cultivate carrots in the backyard. They need to have had a regulation barring multi-family dwellings. Do you remember those two stunning elm trees that were over there? When Biff and I strung the swing between them, we hung it between their legs.²³

Linda replies that it was like being a million miles from the city. Elm trees are symptomatic of a rural lifestyle, and their removal from an agrarian setup to an industrial zone is a paradigm shift from beauty to ugliness. Willy Loman’s fury can be observed in the phrase, “they should’ve arrested the builder for cutting those down,” which can be seen in the passage. They slaughtered everyone in the neighborhood. When it was still lilac and wisteria at this time of the year, I look back to those days with you, Linda. And then the peonies and the daffodils would emerge from their hiding places. What a wonderful aroma to fill the space!²⁴

Linda reasons that the state has to accommodate people somehow, but Loman is critical of the process of urbanization in the name of progress. According to him, “there are more people. This is the problem that is bringing this country to its knees! The population is rapidly expanding beyond any reasonable limits. The level of competition is excruciating.

One might get a whiff of the stench coming from the apartment buildings. She gives him hope for a better future and says, "On a warm Sunday, we'll drive in the country." to help him cope with his despair. And then I'll roll down the window, and we'll eat our lunch." Willy responds negatively, saying, "No, the windshields on the new cars do not open"²⁵. The elm trees that loom so large in Willy's imagination remind him of his close association with Nature. Consequently, he consistently experienced a sense of residing near nature rather than being immersed in it.

The phenomenon of urban sprawl arises from corporate culture's subversion of fundamental architectural principles, leading to its dominance in suburban expansion. This results in the business tycoons, not the architects, who plan a city, leading to the undesirable characteristics of sprawl. The Marketecture that emerges as a result of sprawl focuses solely on maximizing corporate profit, irrespective of any potential adverse effects. In other words, it is yet another example of the phenomenon known as inversion, which pertains to human subjugation in the presence of productivity. The outcome manifests as a space replete with architectural abominations, wherein the various ailments commonly induced by an imbalanced market are vividly highlighted for the observer. Indeed, the characters refer to that location as their domicile.

The genuine essence of commodifying marketecture transforms a town's central activities due to the sprawl phenomena during the past five decades. The transformation of the public space has resulted in a shift from traditional town squares to commercial establishments such as retail malls and restaurants. As restaurants are a far more productive commercial experience, they extract consumer dollars from their pockets and sap them of their cultural associations.

This phenomenon has made the environment bereft of all beauty. Going from one town to another is one of the joyless promenades. Hence, Willy Loman is very alone out there on a narrow highway. To make that money, he is on the roads always. As soon as he entered the house, he unlocked the door, went into the kitchen, and relieved himself of his load despite the discomfort in his hand. After being interrogated about the events that had unfolded, he responded, "I progressed until a slightly elevated position beyond the vicinity of Yonkers."²⁶ Upon consuming a serving of coffee, I discovered that I was unable to sustain my driving activity. The automobile consistently deviated towards the edge of the roadway. She explained her feelings of loneliness, particularly during periods of low business activity when there is a lack of social interaction. The sentiment expressed by the author in Miller's work from 1958 suggests a sense of pessimism over the prospect of future sales and the ability to generate income for oneself, as well as for others or a commercial entity, particularly one that benefits a particular group of individuals. The statement is attributed to the author. The explosive nature of Willy is often highlighted throughout the text. The subject exhibits a deep affection for the object, surpassing mere love and extending into admiration. This admiration is evoked by the object's capricious

disposition, temperament, ambitious aspirations, and minor acts of unkindness. These characteristics serve as poignant reminders to the subject of the intense desires that reside within the object, desires that the subject also possesses but lacks the emotional fortitude to express and pursue to their ultimate fulfillment. Willy announces as he walks in, "I am so exhausted I could die."²⁷ I was unable to be there. I'm sorry, Linda, but I just couldn't make it.

According to Linda, "He drives seven hundred miles, and by the time he gets there, no one recognizes him or is happy to see him."²⁸ And what passes through the thoughts of a man while he is driving home a distance of seven hundred miles without earning a single cent? Once more, he totaled his car in an accident. There was a visit from the insurance inspector. He stated that they have evidences in their possession. That none of these mishaps that occurred over the past year were indeed mishaps.

According to Wright, progress does not necessarily need to wreak havoc on the landscape as long as it serves a higher set of ideals, including aesthetic, moral, spiritual, and cultural considerations. Failure to achieve this outcome will disrupt the inherent balance, resulting in severe consequences for the individuals inhabiting the affected environment. As previously noted by Wright, the surrounding environment has a significant role in shaping individuals' ideals and reinforcing their values. The impact of our surroundings extends to various aspects of our lives, including our character, well-being, and perspective on life. This influence is present at different levels, ranging from individual households to expansive public areas. The cultivation of character, well-being, and perspective is influenced by it.

In the story, Biff believes that I am experiencing a sense of discontentment as I perceive the individuals in my surroundings to be disingenuous, leading me to compromise my personal standards and principles consistently. Happy's companion has constructed a gorgeous residence and asserts, "indeed, whenever he enters a retail establishment, the surrounding individuals instinctively create a path for him to traverse."²⁹ I aspire to enter the store with the same gait that he does. He exhibits an excessively heightened inclination toward rivalry, leading him to engage in infidelity with his executive's fiancé. This behaviour may stem from an overdeveloped feeling of competitiveness, as I undermined their relationship's integrity.

The state of bliss experienced by Happy Loman is also characterized by its fragility. He expresses that he finds himself within his dwelling on certain occasions, devoid of any company. Furthermore, I contemplate the financial obligation I am incurring through the payment of rent. This phenomenon is remarkable. However, it is the desired outcome that I have consistently sought. I possess a personal residence, an automobile, and many female acquaintances. Nevertheless, I am experiencing a profound sense of loneliness. Biff, akin to his father, engages in agricultural pursuits while also embodying the creative

inclinations inherited from his grandfather. While Happy never attempts to delve into his inner self to find a sense of detachment from his own being or the natural world. Biff suggests the possibility of purchasing a ranch. Engage in the practice of cow husbandry, employing our physical might. Individuals with a physique similar to mine ought to engage in physical exercise in outdoor environments³⁰.

More than a business tycoon, Howard is a technological fundamentalist playing with a newly bought tape recorder. Willy enters his office unnoticed by him. When Willy seeks his attention, he tells him how crazy he has been about this new machine. He says, "the most terrific machine I ever saw. I was up all night with it." For him, the machine is "the fascinating relaxation". When Willy shares his problem with him and requests a bit of relaxation in the Nature of duties assigned to him, Howard is adamant and refuses straightaway, saying that "I cannot take blood out of a stone" and fires him. Willy had to bargain himself in Howards' office. Dejected and depressed, he sees his sons waiting in a restaurant for him, starts chasing call girls, and refuses to recognize their father. The final step of suicide taken by Willy Loman is the ultimate defiance against the constructing environment wrongly chosen by him³¹.

Biff is conscious of who he is. He confides in his mother, saying, "it's just you see, mom, I don't fit in the business." Not that I won't make an effort. I'll give it a shot and promise I'll succeed". "I don't care what they think!" Biff exclaimed. They have been making fun of Dad for years, and you know why they do it. Because this city is a mental asylum, and we don't belong here! Cement should be mixed on some open planes or carpenters, and we should be doing that. It's okay for a carpenter to blow his whistle! Miller published his study in 1958.³²

Their language also provides insight into the degree to which they have been ingrained in a material culture. When cheerful is considering starting a business, he thinks selling sporting items is fantastic. It was just brought to my attention again. You and I, Biff — together, we have the Loman line. We put in a couple weeks of training and then performed in a few different exhibitions.³³

The Market's concept is integrated into the environment in several different ways, including the commercialization of trees, the homogenization of buildings, and the incarceration of inmates, among other things. People flee into the suburbs in response to rising levels of competitiveness and a deterioration in the sense of community shared by residents. In the suburbs, life is centered on the automobile. The increase in commuting time is also attributable to sprawl, which has recently contributed to congestion throughout the entire area. When Willy initially started traveling on roads, his surroundings had green fields. He relives the past when he has to make a business trip to a desolate highway to California. Willy Loman imagines a "so beautiful "landscape up there; the trees are so thick, and the sun is warm. I opened the windshields and just let

the warm air bath over me. And then, suddenly, I'm going off the road! I'm telling you, I forgot I was driving."³⁴

As the availability of open space has diminished, there has been a corresponding decrease in the level of patience exhibited by commuters. The level of tension among commuters has increased significantly. According to Stiles, as cited in Boothroyd, it leads to the emergence of "road rage."³⁵ The concept of the bedroom community emerges as a residential area mostly utilized for sleeping purposes by commuters rather than serving as a fully-fledged place of permanent residence. Willy's engagement in an adulterous relationship with a woman residing in California is a consequence of his transient lifestyle. The protagonist experiences an increasing sense of detachment from his offspring, namely his son Biff, who embodies his ambitious aims and represents his hopes for the future. According to the renowned scholar Robert Putnam³⁶, a notable parallel exists between the decline in community engagement and the erosion of loyalty within corporate entities—the interpersonal dynamics between Happy and his colleagues and superiors.

Willy's family is facing obesity in architecture, just like most people in the United States. Willy chooses to spend the best years of his life commuting to and from work in his automobile so that he can afford the monthly payments on a house rather than leading a straightforward existence with his family in a modest home that caters to their genuine requirements, as a member of a more significant community that is a component of an even more prominent natural environment. He does that because he wants to exhibit his 'conspicuous consumption'³⁷ and feel good about himself. Hence Willy's statement, "figure it out, work a lifetime to pay off a house. You finally own it, and there's nobody to live in it" exhibits the desperation of a person exploited by Marketecture.

Willy is further depressed because he has to pay a lot of money in installments. His salary has been stopped, and he is on commission only and cannot reach the clients, so there is no hope for commissions anymore. And when he comes home, Linda enlists all the installments on various electronics. Linda commences her computations by stating, "The expenditure incurred for the refrigerator amounts to sixty dollars due to the malfunctioning of the fan belt, which was priced at one dollar and eighty cents." The washing machine is priced at \$960, while the vacuum cleaner requires a payment of \$3.50, which is due on the fifteenth of the month. Subsequently, the remaining amount of funds is twenty-one dollars, explicitly referring to the roof. The insurance premium amounts to one hundred and sixty-eight units. She serves as a reminder to him of the financial burden associated with the motor job on the car. You are indebted to the automobile dealer for three and a half units. The miscellaneous items amount to approximately one hundred and twenty dollars by the fifteenth day of the month. Upon learning of the substantial sum of one hundred and twenty dollars, the individual displays a state of astonishment. If the business does not improve, I am uncertain about the course of action I will take³⁸.

The individual's depressive state is evident from their expression, "I am constantly engaged in a competition with the junkyard." I have recently completed the final payment on the automobile, which is currently in significant deterioration. The refrigerator exhibits an excessive rate of belt consumption. The timing of those entities is conducted. The duration of their usage is measured so that upon completion of payment, they are depleted.³⁹

To which Biff says, "That is a one-million dollar idea!"⁴⁰.

The emergence of Marketecture represents a significant departure from conventional practices. In the past, individuals possessed a greater capacity to influence the design and development of their living spaces prior to the advent of contemporary real estate practices that have introduced market efficiency. The proximity between consumers and developers being consistently minimal led to towns being the cumulative outcome of individual actions. The ultimate outcome entailed the development of communities characterized by a distinct sense of locality and a human-centric environment, alongside the construction of robust residences and villages that individuals sought as places of residence. The final outcome was an architectural design characterised by a multitude of unique and distinct variations, exhibiting a high degree of diversity. As the efficacy of the Market has escalated, individuals have progressively relinquished authority over their immediate surroundings in favor of the Market as a whole. The concept of "home" has transformed into an external entity shaped by decisions made by individuals outside the control of the inhabitants. These options fail to align with our preferences or offer services that enhance our well-being to the same extent; instead, they conform to a predetermined, standardized environment that aims to maximize financial gains from us. The concept of "home" has transformed into an additional commodified entity⁴¹. Home is the consequence of decisions made outside of the inmates. This detracts from the aesthetics of our surroundings and, over time, diminishes the quality of those settings. In order to overlook gaping joints, sloppy measurements and obvious blemishes, Willy Loman recreates the village feel of the past in his dream.

Conclusion:

The play characterizes block-by-block regression of the Americans into ugliness and homogeneity. When it comes to anything, having the Market in command always results in an ugly situation. Certain developments prioritize the maximization of developers' profits over the mitigation of their societal impact, hence potentially limiting the overall satisfaction experienced by society. The aforementioned discussion shed light on the inherent characteristics of our market-oriented society, which is primarily oriented on exploiting individuals for financial gain rather than ensuring their long-term well-being. The fundamental differentiation between a civilization and an economy is as follows. The theatrical production delivers compelling and indisputable empirical evidence that

unequivocally suggests the presence of significant flaws within the free-market paradigm, particularly in areas devoid of vegetation. This information unequivocally demonstrates a significant discrepancy within the framework of free-market ideology. The reason for this is that sprawl, which is the result of unrestrained market forces, is an unavoidable catastrophe. The play's setting takes place on an incredible continent rich in natural resources for the protagonists to utilize. Despite this, the characters are shown engaging in activities such as eating fast food like cheeseburgers, playing with machinery, and breathing polluted air. A world that is not made for humans but rather for the economic system itself, at the expense of humans, has been produced due to unrestrained capitalism's application. This world is becoming less and less livable with each passing day since it is not designed for humans. In principle, the free market seems appealing, but in practice, it has not been able to maximize human happiness.

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